

STUDY OF PURITY OF SOLAR ELEMENTS BY LASER SPECTRAL METHOD

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Abstract. *This work is devoted to the development of highly sensitive methods of laser analytical spectroscopy. Two types of burners, a slot burner and an injection burner, were used for obtain aerosol particles. The presented work is aimed at studying the influence of standard aqueous solutions on the temperature characteristics of combustion of free jets of propane-butane in air. The influence of various NaCl aerosol particles was studied in a propane-butane-air flame. A laser spectral (atom-ionization) method of controlling the combustion process of natural gas was developed. In this work, the flame atom-ionization spectrometer was used for the determination of the content of Cr, Fe, Al, Na and Cs in semiconductor materials of gallium arsenide (GaAs) and silicon (Si). The method of obtaining high purity of semiconductor materials was suggested in the work using “flame” and “rod-flame” atomizers. Each of atomizer has its own preferential domain of application.*

Keywords: *atom, ion, impurity, semiconductor materials, flame, vacuum, laser, ionization signal.*

1. Introduction

With the development of laser technology, methods for ultrasensitive detection of various states of atoms have appeared. Among them, the most promising and developed for practical applications are laser resonance ionization spectroscopy (RIS) in a vacuum [1,2,9, 12], laser-enhanced ionization (LEI) spectroscopy in a flame [3-9, 11,12] and cavity-ringdown laser absorption spectroscopy (CRLAS) [4, 8,10,11].

Chromium, iron, aluminum, cesium and sodium are used in various fields of science and technology. Chromium is a toxic element, and its role in the metabolism of the human body still remains poorly understood. One of the reasons is the lack of a reliable method for assessing the normal concentration of chromium in the human body. Gallium arsenide is a fairly common material currently used in the production of semiconductor devices. As is known, the physical properties of semiconductors primarily depend on the purity of the material due to the fact that impurities create unprogrammed donor and acceptor centers that unpredictably change the properties of the semiconductor. One of the possible impurities of gallium arsenide are chromium, aluminum and iron.

Interest in the study of one-stage and two-stage excitation schemes for Cr, Al and Fe atoms is caused by the fact that spectroscopic data on Rydberg states ($n \geq 4$) lying 0.9÷1.5 eV below the ionization limit are absent in the literature. These data are of both independent scientific interest and can be used in choosing optimal schemes for laser ionization of Cr, Al and Fe atoms. In particular, the determination of these schemes is a necessary step in solving the problem of highly sensitive detection of Cr, Al and Fe atoms by the method of resonant laser ionization spectroscopy.

This work is devoted to the determination of trace amounts of chromium, iron, aluminum, cesium and sodium in aqueous standard solutions of the elements under study and in solutions with a matrix of gallium arsenide and silicon using atomic ionization spectroscopy. Single-stage

and two-stage chromium excitation schemes in a “rod-flame” atomizer were studied. The results obtained can be used in analytical tasks, in particular to determine small concentrations of elements in solutions, especially pure substances, solar cells, semiconductor materials and in the human body.

The idea of the method (Figure 1) is that free atoms of the element being determined, obtained in some way, are selectively excited into high-lying electronic states by radiation from one or several (stepwise excitation through intermediate levels) lasers. Excited atoms (Figure 2) are ionized in various ways, followed by recording of the resulting charged particles.

In recent years, aerosol particles of metals, various aerosols of metal salts, chemical reagents, organic dyes, alloys, soils, rocks and standard solutions and determination of trace elements have begun to be studied most actively [4-7, 9-12].

Various atomizers are demonstrated to study the effect of the sample base on the value of the analytical signal. To solve this problem, we have increased the spectral selectivity of the LEI method by using stepwise excitation of the Au atom [12]. The heating modes of the rod for the determination of chromium, manganese, nickel and cobalt in NH_4F and NaF are shown in [4,6].

2. EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

The scheme of an atomic ionization spectrometer is shown in Figure 3 and has been described earlier [3,13]. It is composed of pumping lasers, a double beam nitrogen laser ($\lambda=337$ nm $\tau=8$ ns, $E=20$ mJ), two tunable dye lasers, an atomization-ionization system, and a registration system. The dye laser was tuned in the range 400 nm -700 nm; output energy of dye laser is 150 μJ ; and width of generation line is ~ 1 cm^{-1} . The free atoms of the element to be determined were obtained by air pressure nebulization of the sample into a slot burner flame. Acetylene-air flames were used in these studies. The sample was consumed at a rate of 1.5 ml/min with a nebulization efficiency of 13%. The signal was detected with a water-cooled collector placed in the flame with a negative potential (1.5 kV) relative to the burner head.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Two types of burners, a slot burner and an injection burner, were used for obtaining aerosol particles (Figure 3). In this work, we used a slot burner from the Saturan device with a length of 11 cm and an injection burner with a sharp nozzle (nozzle diameter is 3.5 mm, burner length is 3 cm) to study the combustion process. The presented work is aimed at studying the influence of standard aqueous solutions on the temperature characteristics of combustion of free jets of propane-butane in air.

Figure 3. Block diagram of atomic ionization spectrometer in a flame

1- nitrogen laser, 2- dye laser, 3- optical mirror, 4- electrode, 5- slot burner (atomizer), 6- solution of the element under study, sample, 7- high voltage source, 8- monochromator, 9- preamplifier, 10- oscilloscope, 12 - photomultiplier, 12- strobe integrator, 13- digital voltmeter

Figure 4. Dependence of particle concentration on NaCl aerosol diameter. Various solutions of 200g/L and 50g/L NaCl were prepared to produce aerosol particles. The results of the study of the dependence of particle concentration on the aerosol diameter are presented in Figure 4. The results of the study are presented in Figure 4. The distribution of particles by diameter is shown in the form of a histogram

The influence of various NaCl aerosol particles was studied in a propane-butane-air flame. The ionization signal during the study of sodium in a propane-butane flame reaches its maximum value at a gas-oxidizer ratio of 0.6 l/min:8 l/min (Figure 5). Figure 6 shows the laminar flame structure.

The maximum ionization signal of Na was measured in a propane-butane-air flame. The optimal ratio of “combustible gas” - “air” was obtained. Using the laser spectral method, it is possible to calculate the amount of heat (Q) released when propane-butane gas burns in a gas burner.

The ionization signal during the study of sodium in a propane-butane flame reaches its maximum value at a gas-oxidizer ratio of 0.48 l/min:5 l/min (Figure 7). Figure 8 presents the structure of a turbulent flame.

At present, production and purity control of ultrapure gallium arsenide and silicon semiconductor materials are urgent problems. It is known that the acceptor and donor centers in semiconductor materials are created by the introductions introduced into the semiconductor material and change its physical properties.

Figure 5. Dependence of the observed signal from the sodium atom in a laminar flame on the pressure of the burning gas.

Figure 6. Laminar flame structure; 1) Gas concentration, 2) Air concentration

Figure 7. Dependence of the observed signal from the sodium atom in a turbulent flame on the pressure of the burning gas

Figure 8. Turbulent flame structure; a) Gas concentration, b) Air concentration, s) Concentration of combustion products

Atoms of elements such as chromium and aluminum are precursors to gallium arsenide material. In this paper, a flame-mode atomic ionization spectrometer was used to quantify chromium, aluminum, iron, sodium, and cesium atoms in silicon (Si) and gallium arsenide (GaAs) semiconductor materials. A method of obtaining ultrapure semiconductor materials is proposed. A method of obtaining ultrapure semiconductor materials is proposed. In the "Flame" atomizer, the one- and two-stage scheme of atomization was studied from the basic state. In all cases, the optimal ratio of "combustible gas" - "air" for atoms is Al, (0.21 l/min:1.3 l/min), Cs (0.21 l/min:6.6 l/min), Na (0.22 L/min:1.7 L/min) was selected. For Cr, and Fe atoms, consumption of acetylene and air was reached to 0.27l/min and 1.6l/min, respectively. The wavelength of the three-stage excitation circuit used and the detection limits for each transition are shown in Table 2. Table 2 shows the results of a study of the theoretical and experimental assessment of the detection limit for Cs, Na, Li, In, Al, Cr, Fe elements in aqueous solutions. The experimentally achieved detection

limits turned out to be about an order of magnitude higher and for some elements several orders of magnitude higher than the calculated ones.

The experimentally achieved detection limits turned out to be about an order of magnitude higher and for some elements several orders of magnitude higher than the calculated ones. Further research is required for these elements. Nevertheless, the experimentally achieved detection limits for all studied elements are an order of magnitude or more lower than the best detection limits obtained by other atomic spectral methods.

TABLE 2

Results of determination and effective transitions of excitation of elements in “flame” and “rod-flame” systems using LEI laser spectrometry

Element	λ_1 , nm	λ_2 , nm	E_i eV	$\Delta E=E_i-E_{j,s}$, eV	Type of atomizer for particles	Detection limit C_{min} , pg/ml	
						ER	ThR
Cs	455	0	3,94	3,94-2,72=1,22	PBA	$(30\pm 1)10^{-3}$ $10\pm 2^*$	0,03
Na	589 589	0 569	5,14	5,14-2,1=3,04 5,14-4,28=0,86	PBA PBA	40 ± 2 $10\pm 2^*$	0,006
Li	670 256	610 0	5,39	5,39-3,83=1,49 5,39-4,83=0,56	C ₂ H ₂ -air C ₂ H ₂ -air	$10\pm 0,3$ 10^2^*	0,002
In	451	571	5,78	5,78-5,19=0,59	C ₂ H ₂ -air	$(40\pm 2)10^{-3}$ $0,5^*$	0,03
Al	396	555	5,98	5,98-5,37=0,61	C ₂ H ₂ -air C ₂ H ₂ - N ₂ O	30 ± 1 $4\pm 0,2$	0,01
Cr	425	426	6,76	6,76- 5,823=0,94	C ₂ H ₂ -air	50 ± 3	0,01
Fe	298	435	7,9	7,9-7,0=0,9	C ₂ H ₂ -air	100 ± 4	0,014

Note. AA-acetylene-air; PBA-propane-butane-air; ANO-acetylene-nitrous oxide; ER-experimental calculation; TR-theoretical calculation; * - C_{min} in a “flame” atomizer, a dye laser pumped by a nitrogen laser.

The atomic ionization method has thermal, spectral and chemical influencing factors. In order to determine the amount of Cr, Fe, Al, Na and Cs in GaAs and Si materials, it is demonstrated the laser step excitation of the atom in the "flame" system by atomizing the sample in the flame under atmospheric conditions. The following spectral lines are used appropriately to excite the atoms of the element.

In the studied substance, the signal amplification coefficient was studied by the addition method. A flame atomizer is the most convenient atomizer for spectral analysis of semiconductor materials. Gallium arsenide and silicon solutions with a concentration of 1 g/l were used for the analysis of semiconductor materials.

It was established that the effect of the GaAs base with a concentration of 10 g/l by the addition method has no effect on the values of the analytical signal observed from Fe, Na, Al and Cr atoms. The detection limit of Al in GaAs samples is determined by the small additive background signal observed from the sample base.

In the determination of Cs and Fe in silicon by the standard addition method, it has been established that there is no effect of the sample base on the values of the analytical signal observed from Cs and Fe. Preliminary assessment of Fe content in Si and GaAs solution with concentration $C=1\text{g/l}$ showed that Fe prime in HNO_3 , HCl acids used for preparation of solutions limited the detection limit of Fe in Si and GaAs solutions to $10^{-3}\%$ level.

To solve this problem, we used special pure acids and reagents and checked the cleanliness of the containers. Therefore, the detection limit of Fe was determined by the fluctuation of the background signal observed from the combination of Si and GaAs in the flame.

There are a number of factors that require the expansion of the scope and practical directions of the work carried out in Uzbekistan on the use of solar energy for energy purposes. When talking about the potential of Uzbekistan in the field of solar energy and the prospects for the development of this sector in our country, the following points can be made.

Currently, effective use of solar energy, which is one of the renewable energy sources, remains one of the main urgent tasks in the whole world, including in our country. The use of renewable energy sources (water, wind, solar, biomass, geothermal energy) is economically promising if it is considered ecologically clean energy [5,8].

It is known that solar collectors use silicon (Si) and gallium arsenide (GaAs) semiconductor materials to convert light into electricity. Although solar collectors based on silicon and gallium arsenide are environmentally friendly, they require a certain amount of money.

At the same time, the useful life of solar collectors with a capacity of 3kW is 15 years. In order to increase the useful duty ratio (FIK) and the useful life of solar collectors, it is necessary to use ultrapure semiconductor materials.

Currently, the creation of ultra-pure semiconductor materials is one of the urgent problems in science and technology. A laser photoionization spectrometer can be used to obtain ultrapure semiconductor materials.

Studies of the dependence of the amplitudes of ionization signals on the radiation energy of a dye laser are very important. Two-step ionization schemes and $\lambda_1=425\text{ nm}$ and $\lambda_2=426\text{ nm}$ for Cr in a rod-flame atomizer were used.

Laser beams have relatively large diameters ($\sim 2\text{ mm}$). The saturation of the ionization signal was clearly observed for Cr atoms when using single-stage excitation (80 kW/cm^2), respectively for 10 ns duration of laser radiation (Figure 9). Atomic-ionization spectrum of chromium in the region $n=6\div 7$ when scanning the second laser in the range between 400-740nm is presented in Figure 10.

To solve practical problems, various atomizers were used: combined, such as "rod-flame", pneumatic spraying of the sample. And as shown, each of them has its own preferred field of application. Due to the high sensitivity and selectivity of the laser LEI method, we investigated various factors affecting the selective ionization signal.

All types of influences are the main ones in the study of specific objects. The results of the study are shown in Table 3.

Figure 9. Dependence of the intensity of ionization signals (U_i) on the power density of laser radiation (W) for chromium atoms

Figure 10. Atomic-ionization spectrum of chromium in the region $n=6\div 7$ when scanning the second laser in the range between 400-740nm

TABLE 3

Influence of the sample base on the value of the analytical signal in different atomizers

Matrix	Element	Introduced, ng/ml	Found by the calibration dependence of the reference aqueous sample, ng/ml	Signal attenuation coefficient compared to aqueous solutions	Content of $\times 10^{-8}\%$, ng/g*	Type of atomizer for particles
GaAs	Cr	60	116	1,93	$(43\pm 2)\times 10^4$	RFA-A
	Fe	1000	1010	1,01	$(16\pm 1)\times 10^5$	RFA-A
Si	Fe	1000	890	0,9	$(1\pm 0,1)\times 10^4$	RFA-A
	Cs	10	11	1,01	$2,2\pm 0,1$	F-PBA

Note. F-PBA - Flame propane-butane-air; RFA-A - Rod-flame acetylene-air; SSP-samples of special purity

4. CONCLUSION

The method is highly sensitive due to the effective suppression of losses associated with the influence of laser radiation scattering and the radiation of the atomizer. The combination of laser stepwise excitation of an atom in the rod-flame system with a flame atomization method of a sample in the atmosphere has been demonstrated to determine the content of elements in standard aqueous solutions and semiconductor materials. The potentials of the method are exemplified by chromium, iron and cesium determinations in silicon (Si) and gallium arsenide (GaAs). The results obtained show that the collisional ionization mechanism is the dominant process.

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